

Effect of manure application and fertilizers N, P, and K application on grain yield and agronomic N efficiency.^a

Application	Treatment						1998 WS		1999 WS		
	Manure			Inorganic			Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	AEN	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	AEN	
	N	P	K	N	P	K					
	(kg ha ⁻¹)			(kg ha ⁻¹)							
0 t M ha ⁻¹	0	0	0	75.0	37.5	37.5	3.6 ± 0.5	48.1	3.6 ± 0.3	48.0	
0 t M ha ⁻¹	0	0	0	112.5	56.3	56.3	3.6 ± 0.1	31.8	4.0 ± 0.6	35.6	
0 t M ha ⁻¹	0	0	0	150.0	75.0	75.0	4.0 ± 0.4	26.9	5.3 ± 0.3	53.1	
1 t PM ha ⁻¹	30	26	14	75.0	37.5	37.5	3.5 ± 33.7	33.7	3.8 ± 0.2	36.0	
1 t PM ha ⁻¹	30	26	14	112.5	56.3	56.3	3.4 ± 0.1	23.6	4.7 ± 0.5	33.1	
1 t PM ha ⁻¹	30	26	14	150.0	75.0	75.0	4.6 ± 0.7	25.6	5.4 ± 0.6	30.2	
2 t PM ha ⁻¹	60	52	28	75.0	37.5	37.5	3.9 ± 0.3	28.7	4.6 ± 0.2	34.5	
2 t PM ha ⁻¹	60	52	28	112.5	56.3	56.3	4.4 ± 0.6	25.6	5.0 ± 0.1	28.7	
2 t PM ha ⁻¹	60	52	28	150.0	75.0	75.0	4.8 ± 0.2	23.1	5.4 ± 0.4	26.0	
3 t PM ha ⁻¹	90	78	42	75.0	37.5	37.5	4.2 ± 0.4	25.3	4.6 ± 0.1	27.7	
3 t PM ha ⁻¹	90	78	42	112.5	56.3	56.3	4.8 ± 0.1	23.9	4.9 ± 0.1	24.3	
3 t PM ha ⁻¹	90	78	42	150.0	75.0	75.0	5.1 ± 0.1	21.4	5.9 ± 0.0	24.4	
4 t PM ha ⁻¹	120	104	56	75.0	37.5	37.5	4.1 ± 0.2	21.2	4.3 ± 0.3	21.9	
4 t PM ha ⁻¹	120	104	56	112.5	56.3	56.3	4.8 ± 0.3	20.5	5.3 ± 0.4	22.7	
4 t PM ha ⁻¹	120	104	56	150.0	75.0	75.0	4.7 ± 0.7	17.3	5.8 ± 0.2	21.4	
7 t FYM ha ⁻¹	35	10.5	35	75.0	37.5	37.5	3.9 ± 0.1	35.5	4.1 ± 0.6	38.7	
7 t FYM ha ⁻¹	35	10.5	35	112.5	56.3	56.3	4.3 ± 0.3	29.1	5.1 ± 0.2	34.9	
7 t FYM ha ⁻¹	35	10.5	35	150.0	75.0	75.0	4.2 ± 0.6	22.7	5.3 ± 0.3	28.8	
Treatment means											
0 t M ha ⁻¹							3.7 ± 0.2 a*	35.6	4.3 ± 0.7 a*	39.6	
1 t M ha ⁻¹							3.8 ± 0.6 ab	27.6	4.6 ± 0.7 ab	33.1	
2 t M ha ⁻¹							4.4 ± 0.4 bcd	25.8	5.0 ± 0.3 bc	29.7	
3 t M ha ⁻¹							4.7 ± 0.4 d	23.5	5.1 ± 0.5 c	25.5	
4 t M ha ⁻¹							4.6 ± 0.3 cd	19.7	5.1 ± 0.6 c	22.0	
7 t FYM ha ⁻¹							4.1 ± 0.2 abc	29.1	4.8 ± 0.6 b	34.1	
	75.0	37.5	37.5	NPK			3.9 ± 0.2 a	32.1	4.2 ± 0.4 a	34.5	
	112.5	56.3	56.3	NPK			4.2 ± 0.6 b	25.7	4.8 ± 0.4 b	29.9	
	150.0	75.0	75.0	NPK			4.6 ± 0.2 c	22.8	5.5 ± 0.2 c	26.1	
Interaction											
Manure × NPK							ns		ns		

^aM = manure, WS = wet season, PM = poultry manure, FYM = farmyard manure, AEN = agronomic N efficiency.

* = significant at 0.05%, ns = not significant.

Adenine, adenosine monophosphate, and cytokinin: nutrients for rice seedling growth in the summer crop season

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Adenine, adenosine monophosphate (AMP), and cytokinin (isopentenyl adenine [IPA], transzeatin [t-Z], and dihydrozeatin [DHZ]) were tested to determine whether they could promote seedling growth of rice variety Tai-Keng 3 in Taiwan. Adenine and AMP are precursors of the

biosynthesis of ATP, nucleic acids, coenzyme A, FAD NAD⁺, and cytokinin. Cytokinin is an inducer of protein synthesis and cell division. Rice seeds were surface-sterilized with 10% NaOCl for 10 min, rinsed with distilled water a few times, and placed under white fluorescent lamps (20 μmol

m⁻² s⁻¹) for germination at 26 °C. Distilled water was replaced daily. Five-day-old germinating seeds were transferred to culture solutions, which included Hoagland solution [Ca(NO₃)₂, 5.0 × 10⁻³ mol L⁻¹; KNO₃, 5.0 × 10⁻³ mol L⁻¹; MgSO₄, 2.0 × 10⁻³ mol L⁻¹; KH₂PO₄, 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol L⁻¹; Fe-

EDTA, 1.18×10^{-5} mol L⁻¹; and micronutrient solution consisting of H₃BO₃, 4.6×10^{-5} mol L⁻¹; MnCl₂ • 4 H₂O, 9.14×10^{-6} mol L⁻¹; ZnSO₄ • 4 H₂O, 7.65×10^{-7} mol L⁻¹; CuSO₄, 7.0×10^{-7} mol L⁻¹; and H₂MoO₄, 1.24×10^{-7} mol L⁻¹; pH 5.0; and in which adenine, AMP, IPA, t-Z, and DHZ were each added to make concentrations from 10⁻⁹ to 10⁻¹⁶ M]. A group of concentrations from each test chemical solution was tested each time and poured into plastic trays (11.5 cm diam, 3.5 cm depth) with two filter papers (Whatman no. 1, 9.0 cm diam) each. At least 15 germinating seeds in each tray were grown under white fluorescent lamps (20 μmol m⁻² s⁻¹) for another 13 d at 26 °C. Each test concentration

contained four replicates. The test solution in each tray was maintained at a sufficient level for seedlings to absorb enough nutrition during the experimental period. At harvest, seedlings from each cultured tray were washed with water (mainly for roots) and blotted with paper tissue. Seed was cut off from each seedling. The shoots were then separated from the roots and each portion was dried in an oven at 70 °C for 24 h. Dried shoots and roots for each cultured tray were weighed separately to provide a unit dry mass. Measured values from a group of concentrations of each test chemical solution were analyzed by Duncan's multiple range test at the 5% level.

Results (Table 1) showed that adenine at 10⁻⁹–10⁻¹² M, AMP at 10⁻¹²–10⁻¹⁴ M, and DHZ at 10⁻⁹–10⁻¹⁵ M were all effective in promoting shoot growth of this rice variety, whereas IPA and t-Z were ineffective and prohibitory, respectively. In root growth (Table 2), only adenine at 10⁻⁹–10⁻¹¹ M was effective; all the others were ineffective. Based on study results, it can be concluded that adenine, AMP, and DHZ mixed with Hoagland nutrient solution at low concentrations can effectively promote rice seedling growth. Among these three chemicals, DHZ is the most effective, but adenine and AMP are cheaper.

Table 1. Effects of adenine, AMP, and cytokinin on shoot growth of rice seedlings and dry shoot weight (mg plant⁻¹).^a

Nutrient	Concentration (M)								
	0	10 ⁻⁹	10 ⁻¹⁰	10 ⁻¹¹	10 ⁻¹²	10 ⁻¹³	10 ⁻¹⁴	10 ⁻¹⁵	10 ⁻¹⁶
Ade	10.2 ± 0.2 b	10.9 ± 0.2 a	11.3 ± 0.2 a	11.2 ± 0.2 a	11.0 ± 0.2 a				
	10.5 ± 0.2 b					10.8 ± 0.2 b	10.9 ± 0.3 b	10.8 ± 0.2 b	10.6 ± 0.2 b
AMP	11.2 ± 0.1 b			10.8 ± 0.1 b	12.0 ± 0.1 a	12.0 ± 0.1 a	11.9 ± 0.1 b		
	10.3 ± 0.1 b							11.0 ± 0.4 b	10.6 ± 0.2 b
IPA	10.7 ± 0.2 a	10.9 ± 0.2 a	11.1 ± 0.2 a	11.3 ± 0.2 a	10.7 ± 0.2 a				
	10.3 ± 0.0 a					10.3 ± 0.0 a	10.7 ± 0.0 a	10.6 ± 0.1 a	10.6 ± 0.1 a
t-Z	11.2 ± 0.1 a	11.3 ± 0.0 a	10.8 ± 0.2 bcd	10.5 ± 0.1 d	10.6 ± 0.3 cd				
	10.6 ± 0.0 a					10.5 ± 0.0 a	10.4 ± 0.0 a	11.0 ± 0.1 a	11.0 ± 0.1 a
DHZ	10.7 ± 0.2 b	11.7 ± 0.1 a	12.0 ± 0.1 a	12.0 ± 0.1 a	11.7 ± 0.1 a				
	10.6 ± 0.2 b					11.5 ± 0.0 a	11.6 ± 0.3 a	11.4 ± 0.2 a	11.3 ± 0.3 b

^aAde = adenine, AMP = adenosine monophosphate, IPA = isopentenyl adenine, t-Z = trans-zeatin, DHZ = dihydrozeatin. Values followed by the same letter are not significantly different; growth period—May to August at 26 °C. In this table, each chemical treatment contained two separate experiments (the upper-row data were from one group of concentrations; the lower-row data were from the other group of concentrations).

Table 2. Effects of adenine, AMP, and cytokinin on root growth of rice seedlings and dry root weight (mg plant⁻¹).^a

Nutrient	Concentration (M)								
	0	10 ⁻⁹	10 ⁻¹⁰	10 ⁻¹¹	10 ⁻¹²	10 ⁻¹³	10 ⁻¹⁴	10 ⁻¹⁵	10 ⁻¹⁶
Ade	3.07 ± 0.0 b	3.34 ± 0.1 a	3.4 ± 0.0 a	3.57 ± 0.0 a	3.21 ± 0.1 a				
	3.65 ± 0.1 a					3.62 ± 0.1 a	3.64 ± 0.0 a	3.60 ± 0.1 a	3.43 ± 0.1 a
AMP	3.44 ± 0.1 a			3.55 ± 0.2 a	3.67 ± 0.0 a	3.60 ± 0.3 a	3.42 ± 0.1 a		
	3.47 ± 0.1 a							3.57 ± 0.1 a	3.35 ± 0.1 a
IPA	3.55 ± 0.3 a	3.82 ± 0.2 a	3.79 ± 0.1 a	3.69 ± 0.0 a	3.36 ± 0.1 a				
	3.78 ± 0.0 a					3.62 ± 0.0 a	3.83 ± 0.0 a	3.76 ± 0.0 a	3.59 ± 0.1 a
t-Z	3.43 ± 0.1 a	3.56 ± 0.1 a	3.56 ± 0.1 a	3.24 ± 0.1 a	3.34 ± 0.1 a				
	3.80 ± 0.0 a					3.70 ± 0.0 a	3.80 ± 0.0 a	3.80 ± 0.0 a	4.00 ± 0.1 a
DHZ	3.26 ± 0.0 a	3.37 ± 0.0 a	3.28 ± 0.1 a	3.33 ± 0.0 a	3.31 ± 0.1 a				
	3.56 ± 0.0 a					3.53 ± 0.1 a	3.37 ± 0.0 a	3.43 ± 0.1 a	3.58 ± 0.1 a

^aValues followed by the same letter are not significantly different. In this table, each chemical treatment contained two separate experiments (the upper-row data were from one group of concentrations; the lower-row data were from the other group of concentrations).